

Guidance Curriculum for Students' Career Development as a better Option in Counselling Service Delivery

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Abstract

Counselling employs a number of approaches in delivering its service to the clients. Individual and group counselling remain the most common mechanisms through which clients are provided with counselling services in schools. However, the ever growing size of students and increasing demand of counselling in secondary school today raised the demand for more options that can cater for the increased demand, better service delivery and development. The paper seeks to discuss guidance curriculum as a better option in the provision of career development service in Nigerian secondary schools. The paper considers available literature and empirical studies and it is concludes that well equip school product with adequate career decision making skills, adequate knowledge about self and existing educational as well as career opportunities in the 21st century will be obtained when guidance curriculum is adopted in counselling service delivery. It is therefore recommended that detailed guidance curriculum for students' career development should be adopted in schools as the best option.

Key words: Curriculum, Guidance, counselling, service delivery, Students

Introduction

Counselling is one of the essential services require in school for it to discharge its expected duties in the society. Counselling is a helping profession and it is the human characteristics that provide the basis for the profession to contribute its special knowledge and skills. Schmidt (2007) defined counselling as a wide selection of services and activities that are choose to help people prevent disabling events, focus on their overall development, and remedy existing concerns. The

purpose of school counselling programme is to provide an array of services that facilitates the development of all students.

School counselling is proactive and preventive in focus being integral to the educational programme as it assists students in acquiring and applying life- long skills through the development of academic, career, self- awareness and interpersonal communication skills. The fundamental objective of counselling is to assist students' transition into adult. To achieve the objectives, counsellors must develop and implement a comprehensive developmental counselling programme that is life skill- based to assist students in developing interpersonal relationship skills, problem solving and decision making skills, an appreciation of each person's uniqueness and acceptance and tolerance of individual differences (Rosemary, 2002).

Counsellors perform their function optimally when basic counselling skills are employed. The basic skills as the prerequisites that cannot be ignored (Azmi, 2008) being crucial that enable the counsellor to employ theories and make exploration; whereas those skills enable client to develop their potentials and make changes in their live. Studies such as that of Bultsma (2012) proved that effective counsellors demonstrate good role model to the client by employing their skills towards improving creativity and life skills of the client. The way through counsellors deliver their functions to clients differ and it is for that reason, the paper seeks to examine guidance curriculum for career development as a better option in service delivery in school setting.

Career Development

Career development can be seen as the totality of work and life roles that an individual takes on in life through which the individual expresses him or herself (Osbon & Zunker, 2006) defined career development as the interaction of psychological, sociological, economic, physical and chance factor that shape the sequences of jobs, occupations or career that a person may engage in throughout a lifetime. Career counselling facilitates the learning for skills, interests, believe, values, work habits and personal qualities that client to create a satisfying life within a constantly changing work environment (Studer, 2005).

The career development and career counselling being provided in schools serve as transition enhancement and Baker (2003) emphasized the importance of providing 'transition enhancement' assistance students as progress toward further education, training or employment. However, Baker recommended that transitions are regular part of high school students' development and counsellors view transitions as a process rather than events or a sequence of events. Professionally trained counsellor is responsible for providing transition enhancement.

Career development is not only importance to individuals; but also a public good of value to the country as a whole. First, career development is important for effectual learning. When individuals make decisions about what they are to learn in a well-informed manner; linked what they learn to their interests, capacities, aspirations, and are then informed about the existing opportunities to which the learning can lead, there is every tendency to be more learners that are successful. Hence, public resources channel to education and training systems may likely yield higher returns. Second, career development is instrument for an effectual labour market. When people discover jobs and career paths ways consistent to their respective potentials and meet their

own set goals, they will be motivated and therefore becomes productive thereby enhancing national growth. Third, career development has significant role in social equity; providing equal opportunities and promoting social integration. Finally, career development raises aspirations as it provides access to less advantaged and privilege individuals in the society to existing opportunities that might otherwise be denied.

One important aspect in career development is qualitative career information as it constitutes an essential factor for good quality and success in the process. However, information needs to cover education and training opportunities, occupations and their characteristics; labour market demand and supply. However, it also needs information about occupational implications of educational decisions, and on the learning pathways that lead to particular occupational destinations. In addition, career development needs information on how opportunities relate to the characteristics and preferences of individuals, so that individuals can identify relevant opportunities. Therefore, information and communication technologies are necessary to be harnessed innovatively with a view to improving the quality, interconnectedness and ease of use of information in career development process as it information is necessary, but not a sufficient condition for career development. Access to information that individual require; understanding of the information, relating it to personal needs at a given situation, and translating the information into action require support of professional counsellors.

The School Counsellor and Career Development

School counsellors are employed and their work is differentiated by attention to age-specific development stages of growth and related interest, task and challenges. Counsellors are human behaviour and relationship specialist who organize their work around fundamental interventions. School counsellors are sensitive to students' developmental needs; work with them over time with hope that their effort will bear fruit at some point. They are held accountable through a standard-based programme that promotes the academic, career and personal-social development of children and youth. School counsellors are an integral part of the education programme as important to the school as teachers and administrator, as an essential to the main function of the school academic success (Sciarra, 2004). Individuals do not, however, undertake their careers in a vacuum, as decisions about future trajectories need to be considered within the context of the broader world (Herr, 2008). Therefore, counsellor play significant role in helping students to make such informed decisions.

The school counsellors assist greatly in preventing losses, avoiding crises and thwarting other calamities that impedes progress in education and life. Thus, adequate prevention paves way for optimal development Preventive and developmental services have the potential to enhance the lives of students in the school (Schmidt, 2008).

Studer (2005) contended that no professional is more vital to the lives of children and adolescent than the professional school counsellor. No other professional has the opportunity to facilitate growth of the youth, advocate for students, assist parent / or guardians, coordinate opportunities for education in the school, consult with community professionals, all with the

purpose of creating a meaningful educational experience for children and adolescent. However, school counsellors assist students with career development in two ways:

(i) Career Planning Programme

Career planning programme is one of the two ways through which school counsellor helps students with career development process. The career planning objectives in school are to provide the students with necessary awareness, knowledge and skills require in the world of work. It is a strategy for making the students aware of what is contain and required in the career of one's choice that match interest and abilities. To help students acquire the knowledge, skills and awareness necessary for effectively managing their career development, counsellor implement systematic and well- coordinated educational and career planning programme (Herr, Cramer & Niles, 2005). They recognize that piecemeal implementation of such programme limits the degree to which they can positively influence students. Herr and Cramer (1998) recommended a five stage planning model for implementing educational and career intervention programme that is specific to career development, similar to ASCA National model

Stage 1: Develop a programme rationale and philosophy

Stage 2: Statement of programme goals and behavioural objectives

Stage 3: Select programme processes

Stage 4: Develop an evaluation design

Stage 5: Identify programme milestone

An important component of stage one involves conducting a need assessment to determine appropriate programme rationale, goals and interventions (Herr & Cramer, 1996). The needs assessment provide the basis for which the programmes outcome can be assessed. The importance of incorporating teachers, students, parents and community participants in the assessment to increase their understanding of and their involvement in the school career development programme cannot be overemphasized. Thus, a properly conducted needs assessment provides a solid foundation on which educational and career intervention can be based.

(ii) Infusing Career Development into Regular Curriculum

Another way of helping students towards developing career is to infuse career development programme the traditional (regular) academic curriculum. Curriculum is an organized programme of learning usually segregated by subject areas contains main categories, content, instruction, assessment and context. Guidance curriculum content can be understood as the information and skills students should learn and it is all the experiences that a learner has under the guidance of school.

Guidance curriculum is structured plans of intended learning outcomes, under planning, skills, behaviour and associated learning experiences, the learning plan is generally organized as a sequenced combination of modules, so that a student can achieve specify educational and career outcomes. The curriculum includes syllabus, teaching guides, assessment guide and required learning resources

Students are taught career development through the regular academic work so as to set career path for them. They will be acquainted with various occupational information as well as

research projects skills to enhance their academic development. Bradley (2007: P.189) gave example with students in English class; the students can conduct research projects to explore a potential career path. In this format, academic development (via engaging in research) and career development (through gathering occupational information) are connected with a writing assignment. However, students learning about government can be introduced to president and legislators not only a historical figure, but also real people with job descriptions and salaries, and as possessing specific job qualifications. The advantage of integrating career and educational planning concept into the curriculum is the enhancement of students' academic and career development.

Conclusion

The job of school counsellor is essential to school system; thus, competency and application of appropriate approach in handling students' career development are highly required coupled with established standard so that the service offered be evaluated. However, career development programme could be affected by the political atmosphere in which school operates. Planners need to be sensitive especially in locations where career development programmes are not clearly connected to student academic achievement. Additionally, support and commitment of school personnel is also very essential, thus marketing of the programme to all stakeholders and integration into goals are important aspect of programme development and implementation. In this direction, clearly defined behavioural objective that address the specific need of the programme participant will be useful in its marketing. Team work to service delivery is equally very essential. Team approach for implementing guidance curriculum towards service delivery is essential in school so that essential partners are carry along for successful delivery. Working with school administration, teachers, supporting staff, parents and community members, the professional school counsellor can add depth and variety of experience to the school's career development programme.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions reached, the following recommendations were made:

1. That since career development is a lifelong process with tasks specification at every stage of development, it is recommended that stakeholders of counselling in secondary school schools should consider adopting guidance curriculum by considering the career planning and infusing career development aspect in the regular curriculum for success career development among students.
2. Information is very vital as far career development is concerned, therefore, information and communication technology facilities should be provided in schools for counsellors used so as to enable disseminate information for students consumption and utilisation.

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